

Structure of Brick Making Industries in India

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Abstract: Now a day brick industries has played a dominant role in the Indian economy. Each and every person has to think that he must be built up his own dream house, because of that bricks industries were established even in rural areas. The bricks industry also comes under small scale industries. Small scale industries constitute the key link in the process of socio economic transformation of under developed social structures. Small scale industries provide substantial scope for increasing employment as they are labour intensive. "A brick is building material use to make walls, pavements and other elements in masonry construction. Traditionally the term brick referred to a unit composed of a clay, but it is now used to denote a any rectangular unit laid in motor". The brick sector in India unorganized and is tremendous in size and spread. India is the second largest brick producer (China dominates with 54 % share) in the world.

Index Terms – Brick Industry, History

I. INTRODUCTION:

Bricks manufacturing has become a big money-making industries in India. Now people of India have slowly adapting the green brick technology (Fly ash Bricks) which is going to be saviour of our mother nature for years to come. Bricks are highly important art of many industries. Small investment big profit making in a brick industries. The bricks industry also comes under small scale industries. Brick industries are generate employment opportunities to the people. It is estimated that Indian has more than 1000000 bricks Kilns producing about 250 billion bricks annually, employing about 15 million workers and consuming about 35 million tons of coal annually. The bricks industries have challenges like rapid increase in brick production ,environmental concerns, use of large quantities of coal in brick kilns, use of good quality agriculture top soil for Brick production ,shortage of workers , increased competition etc

II. THE HISTORY OF BRICKS AND BRICK-MAKING:

The ancient Egyptians also used Sun dried mud. Bricks are building materials evidence of which can still be seen today at ruins such Harappa Buhana and Mohenjodara. These bricks are consisted of 4:2:1 ratio which enabled them to be laid more easily. During 12 century bricks were reintroduced to northern Germany from northern Italy. During the renaissance and baroque periods ,exposed bricks walls become unpopular and bricks work was generally covered by plaster . Only during mid 18th century did visible brick walls again gain some popularity.

III. BRICKS NOW:

Modern machinery, earth moving equipment, power, electronic and modern tunnel kilns, making bricks has become much more productive and efficient. With clay bricks being the more popular, they are now manufactured using 3 processes soft mud, dry press and extruded. Also during 2007 the new "fly ash" bricks was created using by-products from coal power plants. Brick work is also much cheaper than cut stone work. Bricks can be made to any specification in color ,size and shape which makes bricks easier to build with than stone.

IV. BRICK COMPOSITION:

Building bricks are mixture of clay and sand which is mixed with water to create the correct consistency. Sometimes the bricks also have added lime, ash or organic matter which speeds up burning of the brick. The clay mixture is then formed in moulds to the desired specification ready to be dried then burnt in the kiln. Clay: The properties and the quality of bricks depend on the type of clay used.

V. MANUFACTURING PROCESS:

1. The “**soft mud**” process is similar to that of hand-made bricks.
2. The “**stiff mud**” process differs because only enough water to create plasticity is added to the clay, approximately 12% water.
3. The ‘**re-pressing of brick**’ is to re-shape the brick or round of any corners dependant on specification. Both types of soft mud and stiff mud bricks can be re-pressed when they are only partially dried.
4. ‘**Cement bricks**’ made from Portland cement, these bricks are machine moulded into size and shape to match the size of clay bricks. These are extensively used in some regions.
5. **Hollow, Terracotta or Tile** -this type of product can made into practically and size or shape for any kind of use. Blocks made of Terra-Cotta are mixed with sawdust which burns off in the Kiln, but creates as more poroles brick. Terra-cotta can be glazed or unglazed.

VI. TYPES OF BRICKS:

There are literally thousands of different bricks, but they can be broken down into handful of basic types. The vast majority are made from clay and are kiln-fired, facing bricks, wire-cut, stock, handmade, fletton, common, engineering, concrete or calcium, silicate, reclaimed etc. bricks.

VII. COMMON BURNT CLAY BRICKS:

Clay bricks are fired bricks. These are formed by pressing in moulds or by an extrusion and wire cutting process .then these bricks are dried and fired in a kiln.

VIII. SAND LIME BRICKS(CALCIUM SILICATE BRICKS):

These bricks are mixtures of sand and hydrated lime pressed in moulds and cured in a high –pressure steam autoclave.

IX. CONCRETE BRICKS:

Concrete Bricks are mixtures of cement, sand and aggregates vibrated in moulds and steam cured.

X. FLY ASH CLAY BRICKS:

Fly ash is used along with Clay in these Bricks. Fly ash is obtained from boilers of thermal power stations

XI. FIRE CLAY BRICKS:

Fire clay exists at a depth below the surface and is usually mined. Generally, fire clays contain metallic oxides less than surface clays and have more uniform chemical and physical properties.

XII. HAND MADE BRICKS:

Handmade bricks are very desirable and individual in shape and color. This brick is one of the most expensive sorts of brick.

XIII. WIRE-CUT BRICKS:

The clay is extruded and cut by wire into individual bricks.

Brick or S.S.I Importance:

1. Major consideration in promoting the small scale industries relate to some basic economic benefits.
2. Bricks or S.S.I. provide substantial scope for increasing employment as they are labour-intensive.
3. Bricks or S.S.I. require comparatively less capital.
4. Bricks or S.S.I. have lesser gestation period and can easily be set-up in rural and backward areas.
5. The small scale units have been contributing to higher value addition. The value added per rupee of fixed investment in a small unit is 0.96 as against 0.41 in large unit. Production per unit of investment in a small scale is estimated to be 5.60 as against 1.80 in large scale units.
6. The S.S.I. units have accounted for more than 55% of industrial production while using only 9% of imported raw material. Thus S.S.I. help in saving foreign in addition to earning a good amount of foreign exchange through exports.
7. Bricks or S.S.I. require relatively smaller markets to be economical and hence they have an advantage in being set-up as ancillary units.
8. Bricks or S.S.I. represents a stage in economic transition from traditional to modern technology.

XIV. CONCLUSION:

The brick industry is highly a labour intensive industry. Brick industry is providing employment opportunities to a large number of unemployed persons and helping them in generating income, but workers are still lagging behind in some areas. A sufficient number of brick industries have been set-up in different parts of district. Values.

REFERENCES:

1. Agarwal A.N.: Indian Economy, Vikas publishing house, Delhi 1983.
2. Desai Vasant : Problems and Prospects of small scale industries, Himalaya Publishing House, Bombay.
3. Mathur S.P.: Economics S.S.I. Sandeep Prakashan, Delhi, 1979.
4. Akram S.: Development of Small Scale Industries in Bihar, Capital Publishing House, New-Delhi, 1984.
5. Internet Sources
6. Karaman, Gunal, Ersahin (2006)-Assessment Clay of Bricks compressive strength using quantitative
7. Of color components, construction and building materials, p-354